

RELEVANT INDICATORS FOR A DIVERSITY OF STAKEHOLDERS: THE NEED FOR MULTI-SCALE SOCIO-ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENTS OF THE ENERGY TRANSITION

Samuel Marot-Robinson^{1*}, Laura Pérez-Sanchez¹, Alexander de Tomás-Pascual¹, Ramin Soleymani¹, Francesco Lombardi², Guilherme Luz³, Luís M. Fazendeiro⁴, Inês Campos⁵, Stefan Pfenninger², Debora de Souza⁶, Cristina Madrid-López^{1*}.

1 LIVENlab. Institute of Environmental Science and Technology (ICTA-UAB), Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Cerdanyola del Vallès, Spain

2 Department of Engineering Systems and Services, Faculty of Technology, Policy and Management, TU Delft, Delft, Netherlands

3 Instituto Dom Luiz, Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

4 CENSE—Center of Environmental and Sustainability Research, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, Caparica, Portugal

5 cE3c - Centre for Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Changes, Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

6 School of Digital Technologies, Tallinn University, Tallinn, Estonia

*Corresponding authors: samuel.marot@uab.cat, cristina.madrid@uab.cat, Institute of Environmental Science and Technology (ICTA-UAB), Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Carrer de les Columnes s/n, 08193 Cerdanyola del Vallès, Barcelona, Spain

KEYWORDS

Post-normal science, social metabolism, sustainability indicators

ABSTRACT

The energy transition entails changes in social, technical, economic, environmental, and political dimensions across different scales and levels of organisation. Consequently, crafting sustainable energy policies demands engaging stakeholders from various sectors to present diverse legitimate perspectives on this complex issue. This study proposes an assessment of energy transitions using the ENBIOS model, which integrates the structural, technology-based capabilities of life cycle assessments (LCA) to the upscaling functional analysis of the Multi-scale Integrated Accounting of Societal and Ecosystem Metabolism (MuSIASEM) framework.

ENBIOS is tested for a case study with the SEEDS project, to calculate and present a set of useful indicators for different stakeholders (i.e. businesses, farmers, households) related to possible configurations of the electricity system in Portugal. This wholistic methodology enables to identify key benchmarks at various scales (i.e. biomass use in a certain region, land use for a specific technology, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of the country's electricity supply) to assess the feasibility of scenarios and allow trade-off deliberation at the science-policy interface. This post-normal science approach has the objective of developing a stronger energy democracy and enhance decision-making transparency.

INTRODUCTION

The energy transition relies in the deployment of new technologies. This technological shift entails changes in social, technical, economic, environmental, and political dimensions, and may usher in new environmental and social impacts. In the pursuit of designing «greener» infrastructures, environmental assessments often focus on single technology units, like wind turbines or solar farms, and technological assessments are related to energy intensity or efficiency (Ripa et al., 2021). However, these technologies operate within a complex energy system and contribute to an intricate network of energy end-uses. Besides, there is a number of voices and values to be included in decision making related to those technologies. Indeed, the lack of inclusion of social perceptions in energy system design can

result in unforeseen impacts, in lack of support and delay or avoidance of the implementation of energy transition strategies (Süsser et al. 2022)

Policy-informing energy system optimization models (ESOMs) usually generate possible future configurations of infrastructure based on meeting the energy demand of different sectors while minimising costs and emissions. They also obviate, among others, environmental pressures (i.e. water depletion, land use) and sectoral interdependences that are not energy-related (Plazas-Niños et al., 2022).

This study discusses the relevance of choosing indicators for the sake of better decision-making in the energy transition. We aim to answer the research question: **“How can different voices/social values be integrated with energy system model simulations to identify the trade-offs between different technological and management options?”**. To do so, our analysis is based in the post-normal science (PNS) approach, which acknowledges the limitations of quantitative assessments to provide useful insights for decision making in situations of high uncertainty and high stakes (Funtowicz et al., 1994). Following PNS, an extended peer community must be included in the design of the framing of the problem to be analyzed. PNS guided quantitative assessment are more aligned with democracy and transparency in decision-making (Di Felice et al. 2021). Applied to the energy transition, PNS means that there are trade-offs between different alternatives of energy system configurations and those trade-offs are valued differently by different actors. Also, the indicators included in the assessment of an energy system will determine the results of the assessment and the values with which those indicators have been chosen, depend on the people involved in their selection. The work presented here has been developed within the CHIST-ERA project SEEDS (Stakeholder-Based Environmentally-Sustainable and Economically Doable Scenarios for the Energy Transition).

METHODS

We assessed an energy transition scenario in Portugal with two approaches: the structural, technology-based capabilities of Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) and the upscaling functional analysis of the Multi-scale Integrated Accounting of Societal and Ecosystem Metabolism (MuSIASEM) framework (Giampietro and Mayumi 2000). The results are then commented against the values of three different actor profiles.

Definition of personas

We developed our indicator set according to profiles of actors with different values and concerns about Portugal’s energy transition. We defined each of them as a persona, “a fictional, yet realistic, description of a typical or target user of a product” described as if they were real people (Grudin and Pruitt, 2002). In the SEEDS project, three personas were created to represent the project’s stakeholders (de Souza, 2022). Table 1 shows the characteristics of each persona. It presents some of the goals and expectations of each persona regarding information from energy models and potential future energy scenarios.

Table 1: Personas and associated expectations/goals (adapted from de Souza, 2022)

Personas		Goals/expectations
Yuri Barcellos (B)	Academia and non-governmental organisations	B1 Minimize impacts of the energy sector from source to use
		B2 Assess clear and well-detailed information about future energy configuration.
		B3 Demonstrate efficiency & reliability of distributed energy configurations
Emília Cavalcante (C)	Porto municipality planning and policymaking	C1 Review demands of her region per field of actuation
		C2 Assess impacts caused by the implementation of new RES*-based configurations
		C3 Demonstrate the potential of hybrid energy configuration solutions
Walter Diniz (D)	Agricultural Associations and civil society	D1 Portugal should import less energy from the EU
		D2 Help his region benefit from the increasing innovative energy plans
		D3 Forecast production capacities of his region for different renewable sources

* Renewable energy system (RES)

Estimation of impacts with ENBIOS

We selected one energy configuration among a pool of 261 energy configuration results defined with the Calliope framework (Pfenninger and Pickering 2018). This configuration, or “SPORE 0” is the optimal one according to costs. We calculated the environmental impacts of spore 0 with the ENBIOS (Environmental and Bioeconomic Analysis) package (Soleymani et al. 2023), which follows the LCA-MuSIASEM integration proposed by Madrid-López (2021). We followed the Calliope-ENBIOS integration described in De Tomás Pascual et al (2023).

MuSIASEM acknowledges the dependency of socio-ecological systems (SES) on a steady flow of energy and materials (Giampietro et al., 2000). In this framework, the SES is analytically arranged in levels of organization, forming a tree called dendrogram. This analytical organization defines hierarchical pathways (Di Felice et al., 2019) and connects the structural elements -or technologies- to functional elements -which describe the role/function of these technologies in society. Figure 1 shows the MuSIASEM dendrogram defined for the ENBIOS run. In ENBIOS, the lower level of the dendrogram is the structural level (n-3) in Figure 1, where single energy-related technologies are represented. Level n-2 shows an arrangement according to supply types, which are considered as social functions. Level n-1 differentiates carriers to acknowledge the non-substitutability of different forms of energy. Level n-4 helps identify the primary energy sources (PES) associated with each technology (coming from Society or the Ecosphere). These different analytical levels enable the organisation of information and indicators for multiple stakeholders’ perspectives. Some resource flows (i.e., biomass, waste) and funds (i.e., power capacity (PC), labour and land) required by the energy sector, are provided by other sectors (i.e., Agriculture & Forestry, Service & Government, Construction...) which involves a diversity of actors who need to be well-informed on how they can benefit or be impacted by this new energy mix. The purpose of this assessment is to quantify these “end-uses” for the energy sector at different scales, and crosscheck with the personas goals, to verify if they provide useful indicators that represent their concerns and priorities.

Figure 1: Hierarchical pathway of electricity supply

Calliope calculates energy output (in TWh), technology power capacity (in GW), inputs of waste and biomass (in TWh) for each energy system configuration. We included labour for the operation & maintenance of power capacity (the labour for other life cycle stages is excluded) (Nexus database, 2023, Di Felice et al., 2024). The functional unit of this “system wide” LCA is 1 TWh, based on the energy outputs of each technology provided by the Calliope model. To connect the MuSIASEM and the LCA assessments, energy technologies at the level n-3 are linked with life cycle inventories (from Ecoinvent 3.9.1. cut-off database (Wernet et al., 2016)). For the Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) we used the ReCiPe midpoint H 3.7.1 method (Huijbregts et al. 2017) and selected the impact category

Agricultural Land Occupation (LOP), as an illustrative example of the methodology. Data for the MuSIASEM calculations has a different scope from the LCA inventories, as MuSIASEM and LCA have different scopes and semantic definition of technologies. We harmonized the data to the best of our abilities, but in some cases scopes are different. All indicators refer to direct operation use (over the scale of a year) except for agricultural land occupation (ALOP), which considers the whole life cycle, including all the potential land that is competing with other land uses for other societal activities. (i.e., annual crops, urban land, pasture...) (Huijbregts et al., 2017).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the arrangement of indicators in the End-Use Matrix. Level n informs about the total requirements of inputs of the whole energy system, related to the goal of minimizing the impacts of the energy sector from source to use (B1). Level n-1 provides the relative contribution of each input to the electricity supply compared to the whole energy carrier supply. In here we observe for example, that, for this energy system configuration, 68% of the labour required in the energy system is devoted to electricity supply, whereas only 11% of the land. This would be useful to inform about the goal of decreasing the impacts of the RES-based energy configurations (C2).

Table 2: Multi-level Energy Sector End-Use matrix of Portugal for Spore 0. The “X” indicates that the values can’t be added together because they are not equivalent.

Level n: Energy sector	Flows Inputs		Funds Inputs			Output flow
	Waste (kton)	Biomass (kton)	PC (GW)	Labour (Mh)	Agricultural Land Occupation (km ² · Year)	Energy (TWh)
Energy System	185	5141	X	170	21117,6	X
Level n-1: Energy carriers	Waste (kton)	Biomass (kton)	PC (GW)	Labour (Mh)	Agricultural Land Occupation (km ² · Year)	Electricity (TWh)
Electricity (% of energy system)	100%	0,0001%	--	68%	11%	--
Electricity	185	79,9	190*	115	2402	201,5*
Level n-2: Electricity suppliers	Intensive indicators					
	kton/TWh	kton/TWh	GW/TWh	Mh/TWh	km ² · Year /TWh	TWh/TWh
Baseload	72,2	20,6	0,34	0,31	0,2	1
Peaker	0	0	0,19	0,05	0,15	1
Intermittent	0	0	1,1	0,65	13,6	1
Storage	0	0	0,4	1,01E-09	15	1
Import	0	0	0	0	0	1
Level n-3: Electricity technology	Metabolic capacities indicators					
	kton/GW	kton/GW	GW/GW	Mh/GW	km ² · Year/GW	TWh/GW
Hydro	0	0	1	0,26	0,76	5,2
Solar	0	0	1	0,64	14	0,61
Wind	0	0	1	0,43	3,9	3,8
CCGT**	0	0	1	0	0	0
CHP	973	719	1	0,9	0,6	2,9
Batteries	0	0	1	0	6	2,2
Pumped Hydro	0	0	1	2,8E-09	37,8	2,5

* As the power capacity (PC) and the electricity output can’t be added with the values of the other energy carriers, we can’t compare the relative share, thus, we just show the total value.

** The values for CCGT were considered negligible for this scenario, so it was decided to equate them to zero.

Level n-2 describes intensive indicators per unit of electricity produced for different electricity suppliers (baseload, peaker, intermittent, storage, imported). As different demand profiles will require electricity from different suppliers, this level relates to the goals of reaching efficient and reliable distributed energy configurations (B3) and reducing the imports (D1). For example, industries usually show a baseload consumption trend, whereas households have peak consumption morning and evenings. Thus, when increasing or decreasing the share of electricity provided by different suppliers, grid planners can use the information at this level to associate types of supply with socio-environmental constraints, especially in discussing the goal of demonstrating the potential of hybrid energy configuration solutions (C3).

Level n-3 focusses on intensive indicators for different energy technologies. Offering information on resource, labour and land requirements per unit of installed capacity, this level is helpful for discussions about goal C3 just mentioned. For example, it can help energy companies to decide about the implementation of new energy capacities. Because technologies are structures with a regional attribute, at this level, we can perform a regionalised assessment that can be used to discuss goal D2: help a region benefit from the increase of renewables. Table 3 exemplifies the total input requirements for Combined Heat and Power (CHP) plants in two regions of Portugal: North and South. It shows the distribution of the burden of impacts resulting from them and how local actors can benefit from these new infrastructures in terms of labour requirements.

Table 3: Regional end-use matrix for CHP technology

Level n-3: Electricity technologies	Regional extensive indicators					
	Waste (kton)	Biomass (kton)	PC (GW)	Labour (Mh)	ALOP (km ² / Year)	Energy (TWh)
CHP (North)	93,8	43,8	0,096	0,086	0,057	0,282
CHP (South)	91,6	36,1	0,094	0,084	0,057	0,276

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have explored the use of MuSIASEM hierarchical structuring of energy systems for the identification of resource or impact indicators that are relevant for discussions about the energy transition according to different social values. Impact indicators were calculated using an LCA-MuSIASEM integration framework called ENBIOS. We defined goals using the concept of persona and related total and intensive indicators such as waste and biomass input, labour or land use to the goals of each of them. This was presented with a multi-level energy end-use matrix which tracks the flows and funds from other economic sectors impacted by the energy transition (i.e. agriculture, construction, service & government...), informing on the potential benefits or costs of the energy configuration (i.e., in terms of investment of capital, jobs and resource requirements).

The use of multiple types of indicators depending on the scale of analysis provides more precision on the allocation and trade-offs of flow and fund inputs from society, giving well-detailed information of the implications of the energy configuration of a certain scenario. This allows a better identification of trade-off across levels, for example, switching from Hydro to Solar can be beneficial for a region in terms of local job creation (seen at the technology level) whereas increasing intermittency and displacing land use (seen at the supplier level). This is important in prospective analyses of potential energy pathways calculated by energy system models as the deployment of new energy sources and infrastructures will require a re-organisation of current resources, capital, labour and land use. These changes will foreseeably affect the share and type of social and environmental impacts. When these trade-offs are included, the debate between different social values (and their related goals) can be made explicit and useful information provided for a diversity of stakeholders to ensure a good coordination of sustainable technological implementation.

This multi-level matrix that also covers multiple indicators is a useful tool to see simultaneously non-equivalent analytical scopes of complex energy systems. Each scope being relevant for different stakeholder-related personas, it can be used to help identify conflicting socio-environmental transition policies goals. On a more applied term, the mapping of values to specific indicators, can be used in the co-design of new energy configurations, enhancing participation and transparency in decision-making.

LCA perspective addresses activities happening both in Portugal and abroad. However, further work could include a regionalisation of LCI to differentiate between impacts and production factors within and outside Portugal. For example, currently, most of the processes in the technologies supply chain happen outside of Portugal (i.e. China accounts for 80% of PV module production (Hawkins, 2023)).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work (CHIST-ERA-19-CES-004) was funded by Swiss National Science Foundation (195537), the Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT), Portugal (CHIST-ERA/0005/2019), Spanish research Agency through project SEEDS (PCI2020-120710-2) and LIVEN (PID2020-119565RJ-I00) and the Maria de Maeztu Unit (ICTA CEX2019-0940-M); the Catalan Government through the SosteniPra group (2021 SGR 00734); the Estonian Research Council (grant 4-8/20/26).

REFERENCES

- De Souza, Debora Conceição Firmino. 2022. "SEEDS Project - REPORT D3.1 and D3.2." Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6501712>.
- Di Felice, Louisa Jane, Maddalena Ripa, and Mario Giampietro. "An alternative to market-oriented energy models: Nexus patterns across hierarchical levels." *Energy Policy* 126 (2019): 431-443.
- Di Felice, Louisa Jane (2023). Nexus database (Version v2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7543815>
- Di Felice, Louisa Jane, Violeta Cabello, Maddalena Ripa, and Cristina Madrid-Lopez. 2021. "Quantitative Storytelling: Science, Narratives, and Uncertainty in Nexus Innovations." <https://doi.org/10.1177/01622439211053819>, November. SAGE PublicationsSage CA: Los Angeles, CA. doi:10.1177/01622439211053819.
- Di Felice, Louisa (2023). Nexus database (Version v2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7543815>
- Di Felice, Louisa Jane, Laura Pérez-Sánchez, Michele Manfroni, and Mario Giampietro. 2024. "Towards Nexus Thinking in Energy Systems Modelling: A Multi-Scale, Embodied Perspective." *Energy Policy*.
- Funtowicz, Silvio O., and Jerome R. Ravetz. "The worth of a songbird: ecological economics as a post-normal science." *Ecological economics* 10, no. 3 (1994): 197-207.
- Giampietro, Mario, and Kozo Mayumi. 2000. "Multiple-Scale Integrated Assessment of Societal Metabolism: Integrating Biophysical and Economic Representations across Scales." *Population and Environment* 22 (2): 155–210. doi:10.1023/A:1026643707370.
- Hawkins, Sam. 2023. "Solar exports from China increase by a third". Ember <https://ember-climate.org/insights/research/china-solar-exports/#supporting-material>
- Huijbregts, Mark A.J., Zoran J.N. Steinmann, Pieter M.F. Elshout, Gea Stam, Francesca Verones, Marisa Vieira, Michiel Zijp, Anne Hollander, and Rosalie van Zelm. 2017. "ReCiPe2016: A Harmonised Life Cycle Impact Assessment Method at Midpoint and Endpoint Level." *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 22 (2). The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment: 138–47. doi:10.1007/s11367-016-1246-y.
- Madrid Lopez, Cristina. 2021. "Report on Quality Check of Shale Gas Extraction Assessment. Deliverable 6.5. MAGIC-Nexus." <https://magic-nexus.eu/documents/deliverable-65-quantitative-story-telling-shale-gas-extraction>.
- Pfenninger, Stefan, and Bryn Pickering. 2018. "Calliope: A Multi-Scale Energy Systems Modelling Framework." *Journal of Open Source Software* 3 (29): 825. doi:10.21105/joss.00825.
- Plazas-Niño, F. A., N. R. Ortiz-Pimiento, and E. G. Montes-Páez. "National energy system optimization modelling for decarbonization pathways analysis: A systematic literature review." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 162 (2022): 112406.
- Soleymani, Ramin, Alexander de Tomàs Pascual, Miquel Sierra Montoya, Laura Pérez Sánchez, and Cristina Madrid-López. 2023. "ENBIOS: Environmental and Bioeconomic System Analysis." <https://pypi.org/project/enbios/>.
- Süsser, Diana, Nick Martin, Vassilis Stavrakas, Hannes Gaschnig, Laura Talens-Peiró, Alexandros Flamos, Cristina Madrid-López, and Johan Lilliestam. 2022. "Why Energy Models Should Integrate Social and Environmental Factors: Assessing User Needs, Omission Impacts, and Real-World Accuracy in the European Union." *Energy Research & Social Science* 92: 102775. doi:10.1016/j.erss.2022.102775.
- Ripa, M., Di Felice, L.J. and Giampietro, M., (2021). The energy metabolism of post-industrial economies. A framework to account for externalization across scales. *Energy*, 214, p.118943.
- Tomàs-Pascual, Alexander de, Miquel Sierra-Montoya, Rafael Nebot-Medina, Ramin Solemany-Fard, Gara Villalba, Cristina Madrid-López, and ORCID icon. 2023. "Socio-Environmental Metabolic Pattern and Associated Impacts of Energy System Scenarios. Deliverable 2.2. SEEDS Project." Barcelona. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7994038.
- Wernet, Gregor, Christian Bauer, Bernhard Steubing, Jürgen Reinhard, Emilia Moreno-Ruiz, and Bo Weidema. "The ecoinvent database version 3 (part I): overview and methodology." *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 21 (2016): 1218-1230.